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CONTENTS

The Use of Lichens as Bio-Indicators and a Cost-Effective way for Heavy Metals Pollution Monitoring in Ambient Air in The Western Area and Southern Province of Sierra Leone Abdul Sannoh & Ronnie. A.D. Frazer-Williams -----	1-13
Academic Mentorship and Lecturers' Productivity in Public Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria SHITTU, Taofeek Olawale; OLA, Bolanle Adeyemi & ADEPOJU, Funke Femi -----	14-20
Paradoxes of the use of Technologies in Secondary Education System in Africa Femi Sunday Akinwumi & Adeola Iyabosola Ayo-Ayinde -----	21-30
Social Insecurity and Proneness to Get- Rich-Quick-Syndrome among Adolescents in Lagos State, Nigeria: Counselling for National Development A. O. Badejo & Stella Ngozi Chinwuba-Anameje -----	31-40
Design and Production of an Improved Cook Stove with Swinging Combustion Chamber to Enable Refueling for Continuous Operation Sheriff Kamara -----	41-59
Teachers' Welfare as a Veritable Tool for Effectiveness among Public Secondary Schools In Lagos State, Nigeria Ladipo, Sunday Akinremi -----	60-63
Free Education Program in Sub Saharan Africa: A Comparative Analysis of Sierra Leone and Nigeria James VIBBI & Abidat Oluwashola MOHAMMED -----	64-76
Managing Education for Innovation and Security in the Development of Sub-Shara Africa: Policy Formulation and Implementation Option John Oluyemi EGBEBI & Opeyemi Aderonke OYEKAN -----	77-85
Cross-Cultural Influences on Girl-Child Education in Ojo Riverine Area of Lagos State, Nigeria Enitan Omolara Falade & Prof. Olawunmi Ayodeji Badejo -----	86-92
Establishing a School Climate That Prioritizes Child Safety to Promote Sustainable National Development Henry Adewale Odunayo; Nurudeen Olalekan Orunbon & M. O. B. Mohammed -----	93-102
Gender Equality: A Must for Sustainable Development in Africa Aisha Fofana Ibrahim & Claudine Anita Hingston -----	103-110
Teachers' Reward System and Academic Performance of Public Senior Secondary School Students in Lagos State, Nigeria ANIFOWOSHE, Olawale Jamiu & MOHAMMED, M. O. B. -----	111-116

Records Management Practices and Productivity of Academic Heads of Department in Public Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria Afolabi, Abolanle Omotunde; Shittu, Taofeek Olawale & Mohammed, M. O. B. -----	117-124
Estimating Rainfall Intensity Duration-Frequency (IDF) Curves for River Rokel Catchment in Tonkolili District Using Satellite Rainfall Data Amadu Barrie; Osman Koroma & Melvin B Scott -----	125-135
Religious Education, Security Challenges, and National Development in Nigeria Exradallenum Olusegun Akinsanya, Opaaje, Samuel Sunday & Aina, Omololu Olukayode -----	136-147
Integrating Sustainable Water Resources Management Practices into Public University Administration in Lagos State, Nigeria: A Multi-Variable Analysis Adepoju, Funke Femi -----	148-155
Examining the Nexus between Inadequate Educational Facilities as Proxy for Migration and Personal Remittance in Nigeria: Impact on Socio-Economic Development Rufai, Musiliu Dada; Anagun, Adeyemi Michael & Olayide, Bilkis Omolara	156-165

EXAMINING THE NEXUS BETWEEN INADEQUATE EDUCATIONAL FACILITIES AS PROXY FOR MIGRATION AND PERSONAL REMITTANCE IN NIGERIA: IMPACT ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Educational facilities consist of both the physical structure and the variety of building systems, such as mechanical, plumbing, electrical and power, telecommunication, security and fire suppression system but also includes furnishing, materials and supplies, equipment and information technology, as well as various aspects of the building grounds. International economics nowadays are characterized by the interaction of capital and labour, as well as by the rapid changes in these components of production's mobility that are occurring on a worldwide scale. Migration is though simple seen as the movement of a person or group of people from one geographic region to another. Recently, migrants in Nigeria travel for employment and educational purposes to scale up their standard of living. Despite these indices, it can be traced that the basic reason for migration in Nigeria is due to lack of adequate educational facilities. Migration from Nigeria is induced by fee waivers, access to professional and educational training, and research equipment. Two null hypotheses were formulated for the study. The study was anchored on Neo-classical and development theory, and the Theory of New Economics of Labour Migration and Livelihood Approach. The data used for the study were sourced from the 2021 Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the 2022 World Bank Development Indication. An annual time series data over the period of 1990 to 2020 using the log of government expenditure on education as a proxy for migration, the log of personal remittances received, and the log of GDP per capita as a proxy for socio-economic development to form an econometric model. The study adopted the use of a log-log econometric model and was analyzed with the aid of EViews version 9. It was concluded that there is no co-integration, which means that there is a short-run relationship between the socio-economic development, migration, and personal remittance received in Nigeria. Thus, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternate hypothesis. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made that the government should gear up in financing the education sector to catch up with the level of educational facilities in developed nations, and also ensure that entrepreneurs are encouraged to establish jobs that would attract the thronging professional exodus from the nation.

Keywords: Educational Facilities, Migration, Socio-Economic, Development.

1. Introduction

Nigeria, which has a population of about 200 million, has been working to scale the development classification metrics of a developing economy since it gained independence to reach a developmental height commensurate with its prideful nature as the behemoth of Africa. Academics, social workers, donors, decision-makers, and young people seeking employment abroad have become increasingly common in Nigeria in recent years. This

migration of people with the ability to establish other economies and solidify the country's natural mineral wealth might be seen as the third rape of Nigeria, with colonization and the slave trade serving as the first and second rapes, respectively.

In industrialized countries, educational facilities include structures, furnishings, technology, assessment to laboratories, and other amenities that support high-quality instruction and learning. It is believed that tertiary education will instill in students a drive for self-improvement, greatness, and the necessary abilities to contribute as much as possible to the country's economy in all its forms (Gbesoevi, 2021). As such, the remarkable migration that characterizes the modern global system has the power to change the demographic make-up of the world's main cities. However, migration has been a part of human existence for a very long time, hence, this makes it not a recent phenomenon to under study. This averts the contemporary issue in Nigeria of losing more professional staff in the education and health sector to developed nations in search of quality access to educational facilities and a quest to improve the socio-economic standard of living.

International economics nowadays are characterized by the interaction of capital and labour, as well as by the rapid changes in these components of production's mobility that are occurring on a worldwide scale (Metelski & Mihi-Ramrez, 2015; Mihi-Ramrez et al., 2018). These are global migrations of linked workers that have a direct impact on how the global economy develops (Le & Tran-Nam, 2018). One of the biggest direct benefits of migration to the economy comes from remittances sent home by migrants as personal remittances received, which is a function of both their ability and willingness to send home a portion of their wages as well as their earnings. If the work performed by migrants is considered an export, remittances are the portion of the remuneration for the export of labour services that are returned to the country of origin in some way.

Migration is though simple seen as the movement of a person or group of people from one geographic region to another (Ikwuyatum, 2016). Recently, migrants in Nigeria travel for employment and educational purposes to scale up their standard of living (Isiugo-Abanihe & International Organization for Migration, 2016; Flahaux & De Haas, 2016). Monies from migrants were mostly seen as a source of consumption expenditure rather than as investments in companies that sparked economic opportunities and promoted socio-economic development (Brandt & Hagge, 2020). The International Labour Organization (2022) revealed that the rate at which people leave most developing countries for rich countries in search of employment is alarmingly high. International Fund for Agricultural Development (2019) asserts that the money that migrant workers bring home only accounts for 15% of what they earn and that approximately one in nine persons worldwide is supported by this money.

Despite these indices, it can be traced that the basic reason for migration in Nigeria is due to lack of adequate educational facilities (Ise Olorunkanmi et al, 2020). Migration from Nigeria is induced by fee waivers, access to professional and educational training, research equipment, funding, research grants, and scholarship. As such, these factors led to an increase in the number of Nigerian students enrolled at universities across the world, from 2,825 in 2009 to 11,985 in 2019 (International Consultants for Education and Fairs Monitor, 2021). Education is frequently seen as a crucial component in promoting long-term integration processes because it enables immigrants to develop the skills necessary to enter the labour market, and because education systems can aid migrants in understanding the culture and traditions of their new country of residence (Borgonovi & Pokropek, 2019). They further assert that the opinions that native communities have toward immigrants, is however significantly influenced by education as a result of educational facilities.

The majority of developing countries' economies have been identified as being significantly influenced by international remittances as they are densely traced to rural areas, and they are also an essential measure for reducing poverty, redistributing income, and fostering economic progress (Akindolie, 2017). Recent scholarly debate and policy discussions in all academic disciplines, including economic, and educational administration literature, have focused on the issue of how monies from international labour migration as a result of inadequate educational facilities boost socio-economic development (Hussaini & Kabuga, 2018; Jushi et al., 2021). It is from this background the study is deliberate to examine the nexus between migration, and personal remittance received on socio-economic development in Nigeria. As such, the study sets out to determine the effect of migration, personal remittances received on socio-economic development in Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The study adopted the following null hypotheses:

H₀₁: Migration does not affect socio-economic development in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Personal remittances received has no impact on socio-economic development in Nigeria.

2. Selected Existing Literature

The overall concept of migration depicts a dynamic, ever-evolving reality. Since its origin, the phenomenon of migration has taken on a global dimension, with benefits and drawbacks, and it stands as an undeniable aspect of our time that affects social, educational and economic life. People frequently want a larger world through migration. Various forms of migration are accompanied by economic, demographic, cultural, and social transitions that have an impact on the tempo and character of an epidemiological transition in the migratory area (National Research Council, 2012). Migration exposes people to a new spatial context, which could be either advantageous or bad.

To understand the concept of social and economic development, it is pertinent to define development. Development is typically thought of as a condition of improvement. Moreover, the concept is otherwise perceived from economic growth to economic development to socio-economic development, but hitherto the way that economists define the idea of development has evolved over the course of the science (Litwinski, 2017). However, it is defined differently in a variety of situations, including social, political, biological, scientific and technological, as well as literary and linguistic. Development in the socioeconomic sense refers to the enhancement of people's standards of living through increased access to jobs, money, education, and other resources. It is the process of social and economic change depending on environmental and cultural causes.

Although the concept of development is perceived as economic growth, there are numerous ways to define the term "growth" in literature. But there is no consensus on this matter. Development can often be viewed as a process of change or as a purpose (Bellu, 2011). Regarding the first, the phenomena under consideration could be described as a process of improving a system's forms and attaining optimal states through a number of quantitative and qualitative modifications.

Issoufou (2021) asserts that in the Republic of Niger, migration has long been a key source of income. Many young individuals in Niger choose to migrate to better the living conditions for their families. In the study, the World Bank report revealed that 293 million dollars, or 3 percent of Niger's GDP, have been sent by migrants to their family members in Niger in 2019. The unit root test, Engle-Granger cointegration test, vector equilibrium correction method, and certain diagnostic tests on the residuals were among the time series econometric approaches employed in the study to examine the relationship between

remittances and economic growth in Niger. An annual time series data set exposes that to a reasonable rate of adjustment to equilibrium reveals that around 51.62 percent of the gap between the long run and short run is rectified by the error correction term's coefficient. Additionally, *ceteris paribus*, a 10% rise in remittances would result in a 2.03 percent short-term improvement in Niger's GDP.

2.1. Theoretical Framework

2.1.1. Neo-classical and development theory

The migrant syndrome and the cumulative causation theory are also known as the pessimistic theory. The theory captures the main reason for the discrepancy between developed and underdeveloped nations, which is otherwise regarded as migration by pessimists. Otherwise, to the pessimists, migration will cause "the evolution into an uncontrollable depletion of their already meagre supplies of trained man manpower and the healthiest, active, and productive parts of their communities" in the nations where the migrants are from (Papademetriou, 1985). Once more, migrants are mostly educated young people who have little trouble finding employment.

To an extent, even if the households of migrant workers are frequently better off, remittances have a tendency to exacerbate the economic disparity in the nation of origin of the workers (Lipton, 1980). The tendency of remittance-receiving households' exposure to wealth is to alter their local preferences, which raises foreign demand (Lipton, 1980). The neo-classical idea that remittances lessen inequality and poverty is in direct opposition to this. In conclusion, the migratory cumulative theory proposes that migration worsens underdevelopment in migrant-sending societies through various negative feedback processes, which in turn drives future out-migration, so producing the vicious circle of the migrant syndrome (De Haas, 2009).

In reality, these new perspectives entirely flipped the neo-classical and developmental arguments on their heads: the migration was now seen as widening spatial (inter-regional and international) gaps in developmental stages, not as reducing them. According to the historical-structuralist worldview, migration is a "flight from misery" brought on by global capitalism expansion and is therefore innately incapable to address the structural issues that motivate migration. Migration, on the other hand, is thought to make underdevelopment issues worse.

2.1.2. Theory of New Economics of Labour Migration and Livelihood Approach: The Pluralist Perceptions

As a reaction to developmental and neoclassical ideas (the migration optimists) as well as structuralist theory, the new economics of labour migration (NELM) evolved primarily within the American research milieu in the 1980s and 1990s (the migration pessimists). To address the complex realities of the relationships between migration and development, such approaches appeared to be too inflexible and determinist. The NELM model of migration and development is far more nuanced, connecting migration's causes and effects more clearly, and allowing for both positive and negative development responses.

By situating migrant behaviour in a larger societal context and emphasizing the household as the most appropriate decision-making unit rather than the individual (Stark, 1978). In particular, the theory helped revive academic thinking on migration from the developing world (Taylor, 1999). With this novel method, households' risk-sharing behaviour is modelled as a migratory process. To reduce income risks, families appear to be better able to diversify resources than individuals can, such as labour (Stark & David, 1982).

In this method, motivations other than maximizing individual wealth that affect migration decisions are integrated.

Since migrant remittances act as income insurance for households of origin, migration is seen as a household response to income threats (Lucas & Stark, 1985). Theoretically, this can explain why people move even when there aren't significant economic disparities. According to NELM scholars, migration is crucial for contributing to more stable and secure household livelihoods and serving as a potential source of investment capital. This is particularly important given the unreliable credit (capital) and risk (insurance) markets that are prevalent in most developing nations. As a result, migration can be seen as a livelihood strategy to get around various market limitations, potentially allowing households to participate in profitable ventures and enhance their standard of living.

3. Methodology

The plan of study provided by research design enables an accurate evaluation of the cause-and-effect relationship between variables. The purpose of research design, among other benefits, is to control extraneous variable(s), the errors that would be expected from randomization or measurements, and to provide answers on how questions and problems are determined. The research design for the study was ex post facto. The concept was chosen because it examines historical occurrences of an existing state to determine the elements that are connected to specific occurrences of migration, and personal remittances received on socio-economic development by analyzing past events of an existing condition. The data used for the study were sourced from the 2021 Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the 2022 World Bank Development Indication. An annual time series data over the period of 1990 to 2020 using the log of government expenditure on education as a proxy for migration, the log of personal remittances received, and the log of GDP per capita as a proxy for socio-economic development to form an econometric model. The study adopted the use of a log-log econometric model and was analyzed with the aid of EViews version 9.

3.1. Model Specification

Following the work of Hussaini and Kabuga (2018), the study specifies the model based on the variables of the study.

$$\text{LogSED}_t = f(\text{LogMigration}, \text{LogPersonal Remittances Received}) \dots\dots (1)$$

So, to form our multiple regression model, we say:

$$\text{LogSED}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogMig}_t + \beta_2 \text{LogPerRemi} \dots\dots (2)$$

Since we have some variables that could affect socio-economic development but are not captured in the model, then they are explained as the error term which leads to an econometric equation in (3) below:

$$\text{LogSED}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogMig}_t + \beta_2 \text{LogPerRemi} + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots (3)$$

4.1. Empirical Results and Interpretation

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Jarque-Bera	Sum Sq. Dev.
SED	5.066707	0.659897	2.559251	13.06393
Migration	1.791677	0.843889	4.962357	21.36446
PerRem	9.483812	0.959538	3.404355	27.62138

Source: Author's compilation

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables having the mean for socio-economic development as 5.066, migration as 1.791, and personal remittance received as 9.483. Also, the standard deviation revealed that socio-economic development, migration, and personal remittance received 0.659; 0.843, and 0.959; and its Jarque-Bera coefficients as 2.559; 4.962, and 3.404 respectively. The sum of the squared deviation for all the variables was reported to be high.

Several tests like the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, the Phillips-Perron (PP) test, and the Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt, and Shin (KPSS) test are the most frequently used tests for stationarity and unit root in the literature (Shrestha & Bhatta, 2018). Another pre-estimation test was conducted as a result of testing the time series properties of the study's variables using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test. This was done to prevent erroneous regression and to make use of the fact that the dependent variables' lag terms could help combat autocorrelation. The ADF unit root test can be represented numerically as follows:

$$\Delta y_t = \mu + \delta_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i \Delta y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots (4)$$

where:

Δy = the first difference of y_t ; that is $y_t - y_{t-1}$

$\delta = \alpha - 1$

α = coefficient of y_{t-1}

Table 4.2: ADF Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF Statistic	5 % critical value	Prob. value	Lag	Order of Integration
SED	-8.0815	-2.9718	0.0000	7	I(2)
Migration	-4.3455	-2.9862	0.0023	7	I(0)
PerRem	-2.9779	-2.9639	0.0485	7	I(0)

Source: Author's Compilation via Eview9 Output

The ADF null hypothesis suggests that $\delta=0$, and the alternative hypothesis suggests that $\delta<0$; the null hypothesis is rejected if the series is stationary, and the alternative hypothesis prevails if the series has a unit root. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test as shown in table 4.2 indicates that variables for socio-economic development is stationary at second difference; **I(2)**, while migration and personal remittance received are at levels; **I(0)**. Therefore, there is a need to examine the association between socio-economic development, migration, and personal remittance received using the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model and bounds testing procedure.

Table 4.3: ARDL Bound Co-Integration Test

F-Statistic	K	I(0) Bound at 5% Critical	I(1) Bound at 5% Critical
1.8049	2	3.79	4.85

Source: Author's compilation via EViews9

From the ARDL bounds co-integration test above, it was shown that the F-statistic is reported to be 1.8049. Moreover, the study adopts a 5 percent level of significance lower and

upper bound which shows that its lower bound value; $I(0)$ bound is 3.79, while its upper bound; $I(1)$ bound is 4.85. Then, the decision criteria for the bound test states that if the F-statistic is greater than the critical value for the upper bound $I(1)$ at a 5 percent level of significance, then, we conclude that there is co-integration (i.e. there is a long-run relationship). And, if the F-statistic is less than the critical value for the lower bound $I(0)$ at a 5 percent level of significance, then, we conclude that there is no co-integration (i.e. there is a short-run relationship). Therefore, since the results in table 4.3 show that the F-statistic is less than the critical value for the lower bound; $I(0)$ at a 5 percent level of significance, we conclude that there is no co-integration, which means that there is a short-run relationship between the socio-economic development, migration, and personal remittance received in Nigeria.

Thus, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternate hypothesis. This means that the model used for the study is stable and is at equilibrium. The association between the dependent and independent variables were established using the short-run Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The ARDL model used for the study can be expressed in equation 4:

$$\text{LogSED}_t = \varphi_1 \text{LogSED}_t + \beta_1 \text{LogMig}_t + \beta_2 \text{LogMig}_{t-1} + \beta_3 \text{LogPerRemi}_t + \beta_4 \text{LogPerRemi}_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots (5)$$

Table 4.4: ARDL Model Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
SED (-1)	1.111272	0.178631	6.221048	0.0000
SED (-2)	-0.303837	0.158925	-1.911824	0.0703
Migration	0.096965	0.051396	1.886630	0.0738
Migration (-1)	0.026978	0.030058	0.897509	0.3801
Migration (-2)	0.048829	0.029157	1.674679	0.1096
Migration (-3)	-0.067001	0.026866	-2.493918	0.0215
Personal Remittance	0.037562	0.027585	1.361695	0.1884
C	0.453864	0.279669	1.622858	0.1203
R-squared	0.997377		SSR	0.020597
F-statistic	1086.321		Adjusted R-squared	0.996459
Prob. (F-statistic)	0.000000		Durbin-Watson stat	2.146976

Source: Author’s compilation

The ARDL short-run result shows that if migration is increased by one percent, then socio-economic development will be increased by 9.69 percent in the short-run. Its corresponding probability value is not significant at a 5 percent level of significance. Also, if the personal remittance received is increased by one percent, socio-economic development will be increased by 3.75 percent while its corresponding probability value is also not significant at a 5 percent level of significance in the short-run. The constant term of the model represents autonomous socio-economic development which implies that socio-economic development approximately reduces at a constant rate of 45.38 percent between the periods, on the axiom that the regression is zero. Hence, following the results, the ARDL model is then estimated below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 SED_t = & \varphi_1 SED_{t-1} + \varphi_2 SED_{t-2} + \beta_{11} Mig_t + \beta_{12} Mig_{t-1} + \beta_{13} Mig_{t-2} + \beta_{14} Mig_{t-3} \\
 & + \beta_{21} PerRem_t + \varepsilon_t
 \end{aligned}
 \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 SED_t = & 1.11 SED_{t-1} - 0.30 SED_{t-2} + 0.09 Mig_t + 0.02 Mig_{t-1} + 0.04 Mig_{t-2} - 0.06 Mig_{t-3} \\
 & + 0.03 PerRem_t + \varepsilon_t
 \end{aligned}
 \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

Additionally, the result shows that the R-squared is 99.7 percent which means the model is the best fit for the study and that the R-squared percent explains the variability in the dependent variable; socio-economic development. This shows that socio-economic development has a relatively high explanatory power in the model. The probability of the F-Statistic from the model reveals to be 0.0000 which indicates to be less than a 5 percent level of significance. Hence, the study rejects the null hypotheses and accept the alternate hypotheses also concluding that the variables are jointly statistically significant during the period of study.

4.2. Discussion of Findings

The study is aimed to examine the nexus between migration, personal remittance received on socio-economic development in Nigeria between 1980 to 2020. To promote tolerance for diversity and make sure that people do not perceive migration as a threat, education is frequently seen as a crucial component. However, about the mechanisms that support education’s role in encouraging welcoming attitudes toward migration and, specifically, how people with various degrees of education respond to changes in their economic and social environments (Borgonovi & Pokropek, 2019).

To achieve the foregoing, migration do not affect socio-economic development, and if migration increases by one percent, then socio-economic development will be increased by 9.69 percent. This then means the first hypothesis is then rejected. This result corroborates with the findings of the Asian Development Bank and the World Bank (2018). Also, the finding shows that personal remittances received has no impact on socio-economic development in Nigeria. It shows that if personal remittance received is increased by one percent, the nation’s socio-economic development will be increased by 3.75 percent. As such, the corresponding probability reveals not to be significant at a 5 percent level of significance in short-run. The hypothesis two result shows to be consistent with Ndusika and Dawodu (2019), and Adeleye et al (2021).

5. Conclusion

The phenomenon of Nigerian immigrants, seen as an escape from domestic poverty and depletion of human capital, is in some ways beneficial for the nation. The study aims to address operational challenges associated with migration, advance understanding of migration issues, promote social and economic development through migration, and indicate the need for adequate educational facilities as a proxy for increase in the migrant’s well-being and human dignity. It also fills a research gap by combining empirical research and practical knowledge. Thus, there is a continuing need for the production of quantitative data and its evaluation about migration policies that address the true consequences of movement on labour migration and national socio-economic growth. Therefore, it is important to note that while worker remittance is effective in reducing poverty among recipients of such income expressed in the form of school enrollment, improved health care services, and infant and maternal mortality rate relative to non-recipients, not much could be said about its impact on the macro economy.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made that the government should gear up in financing the education sector to catch up with the level of educational facilities in developed nations, and also ensure that entrepreneurs are encouraged to establish jobs that would attract the thronging professional exodus from the nation.

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